

DELIVERABLE D9.9

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Description
CA	Consortium Agreement
CC	Creative Commons
CRM	Critical Raw Material
D	Deliverable
DMP	Data Management Plan
DoA	Description of Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EEA	European Environment Agency
EOW	End Of Waste
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable
FPSC	Follower Projects Steering Committee
GA	Grant Agreement
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HEU	Horizon Europe
IAB	International Advisory Board
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IT	Information Technology
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
M&Q	Mining and Quarries
MS	Microsoft
N/A	Non-Applicable
OA	Open Access
ORDP	Open Research Data Pilot
OS	Open Science
OSI	Open-Source Initiative

PR	Project Result
PRPs	Project Result per Pillar
PU	Public
R8	ROTATE
RM	Raw Materials
RMIS	RM Information System
RTD	Research and Technical Development
SLO	Social License to Operate
TBD	To Be Defined
TMT	Technical Management Team
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
V	Version
WP	Work Package

1 Introduction

1.1 Project Overview

ROTATE's ambition is to tap the full potential of minerals extraction and processing in a sustainable and ecological way, developing the needed technologies and tools for achieving zero emissions and pollution for essential and critical raw materials (CRM) obtention and ensuring a circular approach by implementing mechanisms for waste valorization in the context of industrial symbiosis, especially reusing waste as various products for the construction sector and recovering secondary products.

ROTATE will deliver specific methods and/or technologies aiming to overcome the reluctance of social agents to the exploitation of CRM deposits thanks to the environmental impact reduction achieved.

1.2 Purpose of the deliverable

The Data Management Plan (DMP) defines all the procedures to handle the data collected or generated and how they are processed and preserved. It describes the approach to make the ROTATE data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable (FAIR) by indicating what data will be generated, collected, and processed, what standards will be applied, how research data will be preserved and what parts of the datasets will be shared for evaluation purposes.

- The initial version D9.9 (M6 February 2023) 1st iteration of Consortium's plan - incrementally developed - on the handling of research data during and after the end of the project: what data is collected, processed and/or generated, which methodology and standards are applied, whether data is to be shared or made open access and how data is curated and preserved.
- The final version D9.10 (M48 August 2026) as a living document, will be produced at the end of the project.

1.3 Intended audience

The dissemination level of this D9.9 deliverable is 'public' (PU). AKKODIS as WP9/Task 9.4 leader is responsible for it, and its main contributor, with the assistance of all partners of the consortium.

Appointed peer reviewers VITO and Citepa for the first deliverable (D9.9).

1.4 Structure of the deliverable and its connection with other work packages/deliverables

This deliverable serves as an entry point for understanding the project-wide approach to data management in the ROTATE project. It provides an overview of data management at the project level, with a stronger focus on research data management as is required by the HEU program.

Figure 1. Stages and WP of the ROTATE project

1.5 Rotate data management with DMPOnline

DMPOnline is a web tool that facilitates the collaboration and sharing of the DMP. Access can be given to people using different profiles: reader, writer, or owner. The site also permits the creation of multiple revisions of the document.

This platform has been chosen for ROTATE to provide an easy and efficient way for partners and Work Package leaders to share their inputs and review them and thereby to have a living document.

2 Data Handled by the Project

ROTATE will handle different types of data which can be organized into four categories:

- Administrative data.
- Open research data.
- Evaluation data.
- Technical data.

This chapter will describe these data categories while providing information on their management and sharing.

2.1 Administrative data

This category refers to the data produced by the project management activities within **WP9**, such as meeting minutes, recordings, internal reports (for historical purposes) and follow-ups. In terms of deliverables, they include:

- D9.1 Project Management Handbook.
- D9.2 Interim progress reports and minutes from meetings (1/4).
- D9.3 Interim progress reports and minutes from meetings (2/4).
- D9.4 Interim progress reports and minutes from meetings (3/4).
- D9.5 Interim progress reports and minutes from meetings (4/4).

The data is collected by the management team, which includes the project coordinator, the WP leaders, and task leaders. It is stored in Microsoft Teams, which is a collaborative application that provides different basic functionalities and extensions. Preliminary guest accounts have been requested for all the members of the Consortium, so they can have access to all available information linked to the Project. The list is updated as needed. This administrative data is confidential and sensitive: this information is available only to the members of the Consortium.

On the other hand, the administrative data refers also to another type of data linked to project management activities, including:

- D9.9 Data Management Plan - DMP (1/2).
- D9.10 Data Management Plan - DMP (2/2).
- D9.11 Deliverable – Gender Action Plan - GAP (1/2).
- D9.11 Deliverable – Gender Action Plan - GAP (2/2).
- Project activities communication, events, and workshops: WP7&8.

This data is open to the public and is accessible via the project website.

2.2 Open Research data

The open research data category refers to the data resulting from the research work. This category includes mostly the deliverables from WP2, WP3 and WP4.

WP2 will consolidate an Open Knowledge Base on:

- CRM processing.
- The treatment of sludge and silt.
- The recovery of disposed tailings produced in the pilot beneficiation plant.

The output deliverable will be:

- D2.3 CRM processing solutions final design.

WP3 goals are:

- To develop new and adapt conventional technologies of horizontal common processes to all RM.
- Explore methodological and managerial solutions for common extraction processes for software modules to be implemented in the environmental platform developed in WP6.

The following reports will be produced as deliverables of research data type:

- D3.5 Open report on new crushability testing method.
- D3.9 Open report on energy efficient AVS tool.
- D3.10 & D3.11 Solutions for common mineral processes report.

WP4 aims to:

- Develop advanced characterization & valorization solutions for enhanced circularity, including valorization of aggregate washing residue in aggregate, cement and concrete products, valorization of technologies for water recovery and for mine tailings.
- Cover standardization, regulation, and certification for construction material.

The output deliverable will be:

- D4.2 Open report on the use of aggregate washing sludge in cement and concrete.
- D4.6 Open report on sludge waste and mine tailings valorization.
- D4.8 Open report on advanced treatment of water.
- D4.9 Paradigm for End-of-Waste criteria and roadmap for its utilization in the construction sector.

The open research data will be accessible to the public via a repository of the Consortium's choice.

2.3 Evaluation data

The evaluation data category includes technical data concerning the quantitative and qualitative evaluations and other related business models for data sharing services. They include PRPs & KPIs measured for the data sharing culture in order to determine a list of requirements that promote data sharing in the context of exploration and collaboration among actors and partners about quarry and RM data.

The evaluation data will be accessible to the public via a repository of the Consortium's choice.

2.4 Technical data

The technical data category includes data related to the technical development of the ROTATE project, which corresponds to the contents of WP5 and WP6.

WP5 will implement the technologies developed within WP2, 3, 4 & 6 in the corresponding pilot sites.

- D5.1 Pilots implementation according to requirements.
- D5.2 Pilots follow up and evaluation of first set of results.
- D5.3 Pilots technical report and achieved results.
- D5.4 Overall assessment of results achieved & KPI analysis.
- D5.5 Open report on results achieved and KPI analysis.
- D5.6 Communication with policy makers & public bodies.

In WP6, the project will evolve towards a platform that includes multiple aspects of the environmental system associated with the M&Q operation to make sustainable decisions for the different operational mine periods and automatically deliver management decisions supporting and recommendations for the M&Q staff by using strategies and guidelines for mine closure and remediation, leading to minimal impact on the local surrounding, strategy development for improved biodiversity, and environmental product declaration. The deliverables include:

- D6.1 Detailed design & development plan for the Environmental Management Platform.
- D6.2 Environmental Management Platform operational.
- D6.3 Mine Closure & Remediation guidelines.
- D6.4 Biodiversity Strategy guidelines.
- D6.5.1 & D6.6 Environmental assessment report.
- D6.7 & D6.8 Emission monitoring report.
- D6.9 Emission Strategy & Energy Efficiency guide.
- D6.10 Risk Assessment computational model & manual.
- D6.11 Open report on Environmental Management platform.

The technical data mentioned above can fall into two categories: Public or Confidential (only for members of the consortium, including the Commission Services).

3 Data Handled by Work Package

3.1 WP1

WP1 has the following objectives:

- Define technical, environmental, social, and economic requirements for RMs extraction, processing, and circularity for extraction sites, in compliance with the European framework.
- Ensure that all objectives are aligned with the project and for each essential and CRM pilot site, with a detailed characterization of critical processes along the extractive and processing value chain.
- Define specific requirements for each Project Result (PR).

	Data / Task 1.1	Data / Task 1.2	Data / Task 1.3	Data / Task 1.4	Data / Task 1.5
Data Origin	Requirements elicitation from the technical, environmental, social & economic requirements definition for RM extraction	Requirements elicitation from the technical, environmental, social & economic requirements definition for RM processing	Requirements elicitation from the technical, environmental, social & economic requirements definition for RM circularity	Requirements elicitation from the 6 modules leaders of the IT platform	Data collection handled in FSC, IAB and all R8
Data Type	Templates for internal use Meeting minutes & video records Pilot deliverables	Templates for internal use Meeting minutes & video records Pilot deliverables - Site information and data Requirement listing from individual task partners	Templates for internal use Meeting minutes & video records Pilot deliverables	Meeting minutes & video records Matrix of requirements, Use cases files (one per module of the IT platform), Requirements for the IT platform (deliverable document)	Name and surname Work e-mail address Work telephone Organization to which you belong Templates for internal use Minutes of meetings Video recordings Deliverables Interim progress reports
Data purpose	Define the RM extraction (Technical, environmental, social & economic)	Define the RM processing (Technical, environmental, social & economic) requirements	Define the RM circularity (Technical, environmental, social & economic)	Define the IT platform developed in the WP6/Task 6.1	Manage and coordinate the project Update the status of development, Communication, and dissemination activities
Which partner will use the data	ALL	ALL	ALL	ANE, CHA, ULI, UPM-M, IMC, AKKIS, VITO, DTI, CIT, CTM, ZAB, SITES	ALL partners
Data processing	Data upload to Zabala MS Teams repository	Data upload to Zabala MS Teams repository	Data upload to Zabala MS Teams repository	Transcription of the video content to text for the meeting minutes Transcription of the Excel files (Matrix of requirements & Use	Storage in an Excel, Word, and PowerPoint file Mailing list (outlook)

				cases) in the D1.4 deliverable	
Data Format	Excel, Word and PowerPoint files format, GIS format, PDF, CSV, photo, and video format	Excel, Word and PowerPoint files format, GIS format, PDF, CSV, photo, and video format	Excel, Word and PowerPoint files format, GIS format, PDF, CSV, photo, and video format	Video, Excel files, Doc files	Excel, Word and PowerPoint files format, GIS format, PDF, photo, and video format
Public/Confidential	Confidential	Confidential	Confidential	Confidential	Public/Confidential
Data harmonization activities required	Data to be used internally in other WP	Data review and merging overlaps with regards to T1.1 and T1.3 needed	Data to be used internally in other WP	Not applicable	Results and benefits of the goals of R8 project to people/organizations not involved in the development of Rotate
Data merging activities required	Zenodo and the data is versioned in the project repository manually by the user	The data is versioned in the project repository manually by the user	Zenodo and the data is versioned in the project repository manually by the user	Not applicable	No, the data is versioned in the project repository manually by the user

Table 1. WP1 - Data handled by task

3.2 WP2

WP2 has the following objectives:

- Develop under Pillar 1.1 for CRM processing a complete mineral processing plant to beneficiate Celestite mineral in an effective and performative way and reach higher final grades.
- Develop a specific high-thickening process for the treatment of sludge and silt produced in the beneficiation process.
- Erect a pilot system on site for the in-line treatment of sludge coming from the pilot beneficiation plant.
- Develop a specific and tailored process path and pilot processing plant for the recovery of disposed tailings produced in the pilot beneficiation plant.

	Data / Task 2.1	Data / Task 2.2	Data / Task 2.3
Data Origin	Lab essay, sample of the pilot plants at the sites, personal data of the persons involved in the project, minutes, reports, and deliverables	Lab essay, sample of the pilot plants at the sites, personal data of the persons involved in the project, minutes, reports, and deliverables	Lab essay, sample of the pilot plants at the sites, personal data of the persons involved in the project, minutes, reports, and deliverables
Data Type	Personal data, documents, emails	Personal data, documents, emails	Personal data, documents, emails
Data purpose	According to the data from the process we will know if we have got our goals	According to the data from the process we will know if we have got our goals	According to the data from the process we will know if we have got our goals
Which partner will use the data	AMP, CI	AMP, CI, ANE	AMP, HOR, ANE
Data processing	All the data will be uploaded to our server	All the data will be uploaded to our server	All the data will be uploaded to our server
Data Format	.docx/.xlsx/.pdf/.pptx/.jpg and probably other	.docx/.xlsx/.pdf/.pptx/.jpg and probably other	.docx/.xlsx/.pdf/.pptx/.jpg and probably other
Public/Confidential	Public only with the partners until we finish the project, then all the data will be public for everyone	Public only with the partners until we finish the project, then all the data will be public for everyone	Public only with the partners until we finish the project, then all the data will be public for everyone
Data storage (location, duration)	Our server. If the company exists	Our server. If the company exists	Our server. If the company exists
Data harmonization activities required	Firstly, we will get all the data from the lab essays and afterwards from the functioning of the pilot plants	Firstly, we will get all the data from the lab essays and afterwards from the functioning of the pilot plants	Firstly, we will get all the data from the lab essays and afterwards from the

			functioning of the pilot plants
Data merging activities required	Not required	Not required	Not required

Table 2. WP2 - Data handled by task.

3.3 WP3

WP3 has the following objectives:

- Develop new and adapt conventional technologies of horizontal common processes to all RM, focused on crushing process and material characterization through innovative methods to reduce environmental footprint and optimize production efficiency and productivity through process control.
- Explore methodological and managerial solutions for common extraction processes for software modules to be implemented in the environmental platform developed in WP6.

	Data / Task 3.1	Data / Task 3.2	Data / Task 3.3	Data / Task 3.4
		<i>Table 3. WP3 – Data handled by task.</i>		
Data Origin	Dust and noise measurements of the environment near prototype and reference mobile crushers. System simulations of the driveline, process measurements and development	Crushability test	Production process	WP1 & pilot sites
Data Type	Dust and noise level data from monitoring equipment, simulation data	Measurements, reports	.csv	Environmental practices & regulations / Information on type of operation / Information on underlying & surrounding environment
Data purpose	To improve the energy-efficiency and develop solutions for lowering dust and noise levels	Crushability test result analysis	The data will be used for statistical analysis, and the result will have the necessary information to control the production process	To develop methodological and managerial solutions for sustainable, safe, and efficient extraction and treatment processes
Which partner will use the data	MO	MO, Task partners	CTM, VELDE	Task 3.4 partners & WP6 partners
Data processing	Data analyzed internally in MO and stored according to common internal standards	Analysis and development of test method	The data will be uploaded to the cloud (platform not selected yet), so it could be consulted anywhere, anytime, in real time	Analysis and conceptual development
Data Format	.csv, .xlsx, .pdf, possibly also other types	.csv, .xlsx, MATLAB files	The basic extension is .csv, but it depends on the selected cloud platform	Data sheets & reports
Public/Confidential	Confidential	Confidential	Confidential	Public
Data storage (location, duration)	MO repository	MO repository	Google Drive (for example), indefinite duration	MS Teams dedicated project folder / duration TBD
Data harmonization activities required	Not required	Not required	Not required	TBD
Data merging activities required	Not required	To be decided	Not required	TBD

3.4 WP4

WP4 has the following objectives:

- Develop advanced characterization & valorization solutions for enhanced circularity, including:
 - valorization of aggregate washing residue in cement and concrete products
 - valorization of technologies for water recovery
 - technologies for valorization of mine tailings.
- Cover standardization, regulation, and certification for construction material.

	Data / Task 4.1	Data / Task 4.2	Data / Task 4.3	Data / Task 4.4	Data / Task 4.5
Data Origin	Experiments at VITO	Test print	Analyzes provided by the pilot site and own research.	Lab essay, sample of the pilot plants at the sites, personal data of the persons involved in the project, minutes, reports, and deliverables	WP1, pilot sites, other tasks in WP4. In some cases, we might generate data ourselves. In all cases, data will origin from laboratory essays, samplings, and analysis of the pilot plants at the sites. Furthermore, the task will involve dealing with personal data of the persons involved in the project, minutes, reports, and deliverables
Data Type	Experimental results, analytical characterization of materials, properties of synthesized materials	Measurements, reports	.csv .pdf	Personal data, documents, emails	Characterization data for different waste stream from the different pilots (total content analysis, leaching tests, material properties), data about the economic value of the waste streams, data/results from tests using the waste products in new materials/products. Personal data, documents, emails
Data purpose	Optimization of the processes within Task 4.1, deliver successful formulation to Task 5.3 (VEL pilot), deliver results for Task 4.5 (DTI EOW criteria)	Characterize a printable material	The geological model will be obtained using various geophysical techniques and hyperspectral imaging	According to the data from the process we will know if we have got our goals	To identify/select the specific waste stream/streams for which End-of-Waste criteria will be developed
Which partner will use the data	VITO, VEL, DTI	CTM, AMP, HOR	CTM	AMP, VITO, FSR	DTI and potentially other WP4 partners

Data processing	Stored locally on VITO servers in organizationally defined folder structure. Data available for consortium partners on request	The data will be uploaded to the cloud (Google Drive), so it could be consulted anywhere, anytime, in real time	The data will be uploaded to the cloud (Google Drive), so it could be consulted anywhere, anytime, in real time	All the data will be uploaded to our server	Analysis and conceptual development. Data will be processed in order to develop a paradigm for use of the selected waste streams as products guaranteeing the fulfilment of environmental criteria at the receptor, based on the well-established principle of the source-pathway-receptor chain. All the data will be uploaded to the shared MS Teams folder
Data Format	xls, pdf, txt, png, hpf, sta	.gcode/.pdf/.xls	.asci .pdf .xls	.docx/.xlsx/.pdf/.pptx/.jpg and probably other	.docx/.xlsx/.pdf/.ppt x/.jpg and probably other
Public/Confidential	Confidential until publication approved by consortium	Confidential	Confidential	Public only with the partners until we finish the project, then all the data will be public for everyone	Confidential unless otherwise agreed upon by the pilot sites
Data storage (location, duration)	Data stored at VITO servers until deleted upon request	Google Drive (for example), indefinite duration	Google Drive (for example), indefinite duration	Our server. As long as the company exists	All the data will be uploaded to the shared MS Teams folder for the entire duration of the project
Data harmonization activities required	Not required. All necessary data for Task 4.1 will be generated at VITO	Not required	Not required	Not required	Not required
Data merging activities required	Not required. All necessary data for Task 4.1 will be generated at VITO	Not required	Not required	Not required	Not currently required.

Table 4. WP4 – Data handled by task.

3.5 WP5

WP5 has the following objectives:

- Successfully implement the technologies developed within WP2, 3, 4 & 6 in the corresponding pilot sites.
- Carryout the assessment and monitoring of the relevant KPIs of each pilot.
- Reduce the environmental footprint and improve efficiency and circularity.
- Set requirements for policymakers communications.

	Data / Task 5.1	Data / Task 5.2	Data / Task 5.3	Data / Task 5.4	Data / Task 5.5	Data / Task 5.6	Data / Task 5.7
Data Origin	Semi-industrial tests	Pilot site: Hormisoria	Pilot site: Velde	FRS Pilot site	Pilot Site: Cimpor	Task 1.1, WP 5, Task 6.1 & pilot sites	Data collection handled in all R8 project
Data Type	% Recovery, mineral phases concentration in samples analyzed by XRD with the software TOPAS	1- Production and operation parameters 2- Results obtained at the end of the pilot process	(PRP1.2.c : infrastructure drawing, energy consumption and CO2 emissions) – (PRP2.1.a: Filler from washing residues. waist amount in percentage and results of full-scale test)	Environmental follow up (water study, dust emission, production / process data...) Environmental authorization Impact studies Minutes of meetings Topographic data Sensors for dust measurements	1- Production and operation parameters 2- Results obtained at the end of the pilot process	Cartographic and satellite images, Certified testing methods results, Physicochemical and environmental characterization analysis, Statistical data	Name and surname Work e-mail address Work telephone Organization to which you belong Templates for internal use Minutes of meetings Video recordings Deliverables
Data purpose	According to the data from the process we will know if we have got our goals	Validation of the process and data sharing with partners	Validation of technologies.	Provider of data for other partners and tasks	Validation of the process and data sharing with partners	To correlate the KPIs defined and final results of the pilot in comparison with initial phase (state 0), considering the expected impacts	Update the status of development and dissemination and Communication strategy
Which partner will use the data	AMP, CTM	AMP, CTM, and partners	CTM, VITO	ALL partners	All partners	Task 5.6 and Task 7.7 partners	ALL partners
Data processing	All data will be uploaded to the laboratory's PC.	---	Data will be saved in Velde's PCs.	Tailor-made software AMBRE	---	Analysis and synthesis of data	Storage in an Excel file Mailing list (outlook)
Data Format	.docx/.xlsx/.pdf / .jpg/ .txt/ .xrdml/.raw/.xy/	Suit office, .dwg/ sketchup	.docx/.xlsx/.pdf / .jpg/ .txt/ .xrdml/.raw/.xy/	.doc, .pdf, .xls, AMBRE, .dxf, .dwg, .csv	.docx/.xlsx/.pdf / .jpg	Technical data sheets & Reports. Adobe Acrobat Reader (.pdf), MS Excel (.xls/.xlsx), MS Word (.doc/.docx), ArcGIS (.dbf, .prj, .shp, .shx), R (.r)	Excel, Word and PowerPoint files format, email (EML, MSG, RTF, HTML), PDF, photo and videos

Public/ Confidential	Public only with partners until the end of the project. Data of scientific interest will be published in specific journals in Open Access format	Public only with partners until the end of the project. Data of scientific interest will be published in specific journals	Public only with partners until the end of the project. Data of scientific interest will be published in specific journals	Public: authorization & regulation Confidential: research data & process	Public only with partners until the end of the project. Data of scientific interest will be published in specific journals. Confidential = process data	TBD / certain parts may be confidential	Public
Data storage (location, duration)	Our computers. As long as the company exists	Company server as long as the company exists	MS Teams dedicated folder for the duration of the project and Velde's PCs, as long as the company exists	Paper / Teams of the R8 project / Google suite	Company server as long as the company exists	MS Teams dedicated folder for the duration of the project	R8 & ANEFA project Teams repository project duration
Data harmonization activities required	From the data obtained in the laboratories, the results will be validated on site in this task. Depending on the results obtained, they can be extrapolated to larger scales and even to other industries	---		TBD		From the data obtained from CTM and VITO, the results will be validated on site in this task. Depending on the results obtained, they can be extrapolated to larger scales and even to other industries	
Data merging activities required		---		TBD		TBD	Zenodo and the data is versioned in the project repository manually by the user

Table 5. WP5 – Data handled by task.

3.6 WP6

WP6 has the following objective:

Create an integrated environmental management platform that includes multiple aspect of the environmental system associated with the M&Q operation to make sustainable decisions for the different operational mine periods and automatically deliver management decisions support and recommendations for M&Q staff by using strategies and guidelines for mine closure and remediation, leading to minimal impact on the local surrounding, strategy development for improved biodiversity, and environmental product declaration.

	Data / Task 6.1	Data / Task 6.2	Data / Task 6.3	Data / Task 6.4	Data / Task 6.5	Data / Task 6.6
Data Origin	Development of the IT platform specified in the WP1 / T1.4	Review of the restoration and operation projects of individual pilot sites	On site habitat-species mapping / EU-Corine Landcover / EU-Lucas Landcover /ERAS-Satellite/COPERNI CUS- Sentinelles - Carbon stock Literature review - Carbon Stock Field measurements - Restoration potential Literature review	UPM-E: Sites, public databases, in-situ measurements CHA & ROC: Sites specific data and Measurements (Production, Consumables and Site Configuration), Environmental Databases ICL: Sites specific data and Measurements (Production, Consumables and Site Configuration), Environmental Databases and data produced by other partners	Demanded in the WP1 / T1.1 to T1.4 including the data coming from the sites: Sites specific data and Measurements (Production, Consumables and Site Configuration), public databases, T6.1 and T6.4 outputs	Sites, public databases, Emission estimation platform (Task 6.5)
Data Type	Source code	Documents	Spatial (glocalization) - Numeric-Description	UPM-E: Numeric and descriptions CHA & ROC: Numeric and Descriptions ICL: Numeric Description	Numeric and descriptions	Numeric. Also, descriptions of the sites will be employed in order to define the conceptual exposure models
Data purpose	Results of the software development	Analyze them in order to program actions on the basis of these projects	The data will be used to calibrate the habitat-biodiversity-CSTock model/ The data will be used to feed the decision-tool module on ecosystem restoration options and biodiversity, ecosystem services-carbon tradeoffs.	UPM-E: The data will be used to feed the energy efficiency module of the platform. CHA & ROC: Environmental and Process Performance Estimation ICL: Multi-Criteria Decision Making	The data will be used to feed the emission estimation module of the platform and to develop the next deliverables: D6.7 - 6.8 Emission monitoring reports and D6.9 Emission Strategy & Energy Efficiency guide	The data will be employed to perform calculations about the fate and transport of harmful substances, the exposure of potential receptors and its risk characterization
Which partner will use the data	R8 Pilot sites where the IT platform will be deployed	All pilot sites	ULI to develop analysis / All sites where the biodiversity module will be implemented	"UPM-E: Akkodis to produce the software module. Then, the sites to evaluate their energy status	Akkodis to produce the software module. Then, the sites to evaluate their emissions. Task 6.4. And Task 6.6 Environmental	UPM-M

					risks prediction and management	
Data processing	Compilation & Packaging	Remain with the CTM	ULi internal data center / Software platform	CHA & ROC: R8 Pilot sites where the IT platform (AKKODIS) will be deployed ICL: R8 Pilot sites where the IT platform (AKKODIS) will be deployed "	The data will be managed via the software platform (Emission estimation module)	The data contained in the databases will be accessible to perform calculations inside the model
Data Format	TBD	pdf , word	".txt, .xlsx, .pdf, .pdf,.tif,.csvn.shp,.g pkg,.rmd	"UPM-E: The data will be managed via the software platform	.txt, .xlsx .pdf, .jpeg, .ppt	.csv, .txt, .xlsx

Table 6. WP6 – Data handled by task.

3.7 WP7

WP7 has the following objectives:

Implement the project's Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation (DC&E) strategies, during the project lifetime in close cooperation with WPs 5&8.

- Dissemination and Communication activities oriented to show results and their impact towards target audiences.
- Exploitation actions to establish the main pillars for a future market uptake plan for the results generated. The exploitation strategy will identify technical choices towards the most promising directions, widening opportunities for innovation and business and implementing an IPR strategy.

	Data / Task 7.1	Data / Task 7.2	Data / Task 7.3	Data / Task 7.4	Data / Task 7.5	Data / Task 7.6	Data / Task 7.7	Data / Task 7.8
Data Origin	Data collection handled in all R8	Data collection handled in all R8	Questionnaires and workshops	Questionnaires and workshops	Questionnaires and workshops	Questionnaires and workshops	Rotate and CRM & RM EU sites	Data collection handled in all R8
Data Type	Name and surname Work e-mail address Work telephone Organization to which you belong Templates for internal use Minutes of meetings Video recordings Deliverables	Name and surname Work e-mail address Work telephone Organization to which you belong Templates for internal use Minutes of meetings Video recordings Deliverables	Quantitative and qualitative data on products and markets	Quantitative and qualitative data on products and markets	Quantitative and qualitative data on products and markets	Quantitative and qualitative data on products and markets	Quantitative and qualitative data	Name and surname Work e-mail address Work telephone Organization to which you belong Templates for internal use Minutes of meetings Video recordings Deliverables
Data purpose	Update the status of development and dissemination strategy	Update the status of development and communication strategy	Helping partners develop commercial exploitation strategies	Identify CRM & RM EU sites where the project can be replicable	Training of the technologies developed in the project (e.g., workshop, videos)			
Which partner will use the data	ALL partners	ALL partners	G2G and participating partner (in questionnaire & workshop)	G2G and participating partner (in questionnaire & workshop)	G2G and participating partner (in questionnaire & workshop)	G2G and participating partner (in questionnaire & workshop)	TBD	ALL partners
Data processing	Storage in an Excel file Mailing list (outlook)	Storage in an Excel file Mailing list (outlook)	Storage in Excel and Word communicated over email	Storage in Excel and Word communicated over email	Storage in Excel and Word communicated over email	Storage in Excel and Word communicated over email	TBD	Storage in an Excel file Mailing list (outlook)
Data Format	Excel, Word and PowerPoint files format, email (EML, MSG, RTF, HTML), PDF, photo, and videos	Excel, Word and PowerPoint files format, email (EML, MSG, RTF, HTML), PDF, photo, and videos	Excel, Word	Excel, Word	Excel, Word	Excel, Word	TBD	Excel, Word and PowerPoint files format, email (EML, MSG, RTF, HTML), PDF photo and videos
Public/ Confidential	Public	Public	Confidential	Confidential	Confidential	Confidential	TBD	Public

Data storage (location, duration)	R8 & ANEFA project Teams repository		Email, repository?	Email, repository?	Email, repository?	Email, repository?	TBD	
Data harmonization activities required	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	TBD	Yes
Data merging activities required	Zenodo and the data is versioned in the project repository manually by the user	Zenodo and the data is versioned in the project repository manually by the user	N/A	N/A	N/A	N/A	TBD	No, the data is versioned in the project repository manually by the user

Table 7. WP7 – Data handled by task.

3.8 WP8

WP8 has the following objectives:

- Promote an active participation of the stakeholders in the project.
- Build a common understanding of the Social License to Operate (SLO) in EU.
- Develop a plan targeting policy maker.
- Define a Clustering plan to build a collaborative network.
- Ensure transfer of knowledge and cooperation among relevant stakeholders.
- Organize and manage the FPSC - Follower Essential & CRM Projects Steering Committee.

	Data / Task 8.1	Data / Task 8.2	Data / Task 8.3	Data / Task 8.4	Data / Task 8.5
Data Origin	Data collection from pilot sites	Data collection from pilot sites	Data collection handled in all R8	RMIS, FPSC, IAB	Data collection handled in all R8
Data Type	Public and personal, documents, emails	Public and personal, documents, emails	Name and surname Work e-mail address Work telephone Organization to which you belong Public Deliverables	Personal data, documents, emails	Name and surname Work e-mail address Work telephone Organization to which you belong Deliverables
Data purpose	Description of the socio-economic context of each pilot site	Introduce the concept of SLO to local communities	Update the status of development and dissemination activities	Synergies, clustering, networking, cooperation	Update the status of development and dissemination activities
Which partner will use the data	ZABALA	ZABALA	All partners	All	ALL partners
Data processing	Storage in an Excel, Word, and PowerPoint files Mailing list (outlook)	Storage in an Excel, Word, and PowerPoint files Mailing list (outlook)	Storage in an Excel, Word, and PowerPoint file Mailing list (outlook)	All the data will be saved on our server	Storage in an Excel, Word, and PowerPoint file Mailing list (outlook)
Data Format	.docx/.pdf/.pptx/.jpg	.docx/.pdf/.pptx/.jpg	Excel, Word, and PowerPoint files format, email (EML, MSG, RTF, HTML) and PDF	.docx/.pdf/.pptx/.jpg and probably other	Excel, Word, and PowerPoint files format, email (EML, MSG, RTF, HTML) and PDF
Public/Confidential	Public	Public	Public	Public	Public
Data storage (location, duration)	ZABALA project Teams repository Project duration	ZABALA project Teams repository Project duration	R8 & ANEFA project Teams repository Project duration	Server, infinite	R8 & ANEFA project Teams repository Project duration
Data harmonization activities required	Use data from T8.2, T8.3, T8.4, T8.5 and T7.1 and T7.2	Use data from T8.1, T8.3, T8.4, T8.5 and T7.1 and T7.2	Yes	Use data from T8.1, T8.5, T7.1 and T1.5	Yes
Data merging activities required	No	No	No, the data is versioned in the project repository manually by the user	Use and Share use data with T8.1, T8.5, T7.1 and T1.5	No, the data is versioned in the project repository manually by the user

Table 8. WP8 – Data handled by task.

3.9 WP9

WP9 has the following objectives:

- Monitor activities and ensure that the anticipated project outcomes will be in time and in-line with the expected results.
- Comply with legal, contractual, financial, and reporting requirements of Horizon Europe and the EC.
- Monitor and tackle potential risks for project execution.
- To address the Gender Action Plan.

	Data / Task 9.1	Data / Task 9.2	Data / Task 9.3	Data / Task 9.4	Data / Task 9.5
Data Origin	Data collection handled in FSC, IAB and all R8 WP in order to managing the project	Internal work	Data collection handled in all R8 WP in order to managing the project	Data collection handled in all R8 WP in order to write the Data Management Plan	Data collection handled in FSC, IAB and all R8 WP in order to managing the project
Data Type	Name and surname Work e-mail address Work telephone Organization to which you belong Templates for internal use Minutes of meetings Video recordings Deliverables Interim progress reports	Templates for internal use Minutes of meetings Video recordings Deliverables Interim progress reports	Templates for internal use Minutes of meetings Deliverables Interim progress reports		Name and surname Work e-mail address Work telephone Organization to which you belong Public Deliverables
Data purpose	Manage and coordinate the project Update the status of development, Communication, and dissemination activities	Manage and coordinate the project progress Provide support and access to relevant documents to all project participants	Manage and coordinate the project Update the status of potential risk	Inventory of all kinds of data handled within the R8 project	Update the status of development and dissemination activities with IAB and FSC (and outsiders)
Which partner will use the data	All partners	All partners	All partners	All partners	All partners

Data processing	Storage in an Excel, Word, and PowerPoint file Mailing list (outlook)		Storage in an Excel, Word, and PowerPoint file Mailing list (outlook)	List in the Data Management Plan which will be updated all along the project duration	Storage in an Excel, Word, and PowerPoint file Mailing list (outlook)
Data Format	Excel, Word, and PowerPoint files format, email (EML, MSG, RTF, HTML) and PDF	Videos, Excel files, Doc files	Excel, Word, and PowerPoint files format, email (EML, MSG, RTF, HTML) and PDF	Word (.odt/.docx), Excel (.xls/.xlsx), PDF, MP4 videos, PowerPoint	Excel, Word, and PowerPoint files format, email (EML, MSG, RTF, HTML) and PDF
Public/Confidential	Public/Confidential	Confidential	Confidential	Public	Public
Data storage (location, duration)	R8 & ANEFA project Teams repository Project duration	R8 project Teams repository Project duration	R8 & ANEFA project Teams repository Project duration	R8 Teams managed by Zabala	R8 & ANEFA project Teams repository Project duration

Table 9. WP9 - Data handled by task.

4 Methodologies and Standards

This section covers the methodology and standards that will be applied to the project. The first section will present the FAIR principles, a guideline regarding data, and the second section will present the GDPR that concerns the data protection.

4.1 FAIR principles

The FAIR Principles refer to a concise, domain-independent, high-level, and measurable set of guiding principles and practices that apply on a wide range of scientific data or metadata. They are the result of the work of a community of stakeholders representing academia, industry, funding agencies, and scholarly publishers in 2014, which was then adopted the same year by the European Commission as the data guidelines for the Horizon EU framework program. They put “specific emphasis on enhancing the ability of machines to automatically find and use the data, in addition to supporting its reuse by individuals¹.”

The term “FAIR” refers to the characteristics of data or metadata of being Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. In practice, the elements of the FAIR principles are related, but are independent and separable. Any combination of the principles can be applied incrementally. Thus, this modularity of the principles, as well as their distinction between data and metadata, facilitates their support in a wide range of special circumstances. The FAIR principles can also be applied to non-data assets which need to be identified, described, discovered, and reused in the same manner as data.

These principles constitute a general guide to the “FAIRness” of data. However, they themselves are not a standard or a specification. To be more precise, they precede implementation choices and do not necessarily suggest any specific implementation solutions. Instead, they act as a guide for data implementers, publishers, and managers to evaluate whether their particular implementation choices are rendering their digital research artefacts “FAIR”. They form the basis for a long-term care of valuable digital assets composed by the data produced by the research project, while keeping the goal of being discovered and re-used by another research.

Given the definitions of “FAIRness”, there is however a clear distinction between FAIR data and Open data, as the former does not necessarily imply the latter². Indeed, while the openness of data is encouraged within Horizon EU program, there are necessary and legitimate reasons to restrict access to certain data. Nonetheless, the “FAIR” principles can still apply equally to restricted data or internal data of an organization, in order to make them more usable and of greater value. Following the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary”, research

¹ <https://www.nature.com/articles/sdata201618>

² https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf

data should be open by default, while setting a variable degree of openness. As illustrated by Figure 2, the more data becomes both open and “FAIR”, the higher the benefits they bring.

Figure 2. The relationship between FAIR and Open³

In general terms, the research data produced within Horizon EU should be “FAIR”. In the following sub-sections, the guiding principles of each one of the four concepts of “FAIR” are exposed. We are also detailing how ROTATE will fulfill the requirements of “FAIR” principles.

4.1.1 Making data Findable

To be “Findable”

- (meta)data is assigned a globally unique and persistent identifier.
(Section F1 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)
- Data is described with rich metadata (defined by R1 below).
(Section F2 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)
- Metadata clearly and explicitly includes the identifier of the data it describes.
(Section F3 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)
- (meta)data is registered or indexed in a searchable resource.
(Section F4 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)

ROTATE as an H2020 project is obliged to provide a continuously updated Data Management Plan (DMP) that describes what data the project will use and produce, whether and how the data produced will be exploited or made (openly) accessible for verification and re-use, and how the data will be curated and preserved after the end of the project. Open data must be put into a public (research data) repository and for this matter ROTATE will use Zenodo (*see figure below*). The repository should be OpenAIRE-compliant to enable the harvesting of metadata.

³ from <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/7769a148-f1f6-11e8-9982-01aa75ed71a1> page 21

Figure 3. ROTATE Zenodo repository⁴

4.1.2 Making data Accessible

To be “Accessible” means:

- (meta)data is retrievable by their identifier using a standardized communications protocol.
(Section A1 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)
- the protocol is open, free, and universally implementable.
(Section A1.1 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)
- the protocol allows for an authentication and authorization procedure, where necessary.
(Section A1.2 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)
- metadata is accessible, even when the data is no longer available.
(Section A2 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)

In compliance with the Horizon EU rules regarding Open Access (OA) (cf. 4.1 infra) to scientific literature, ROTATE will make any scientific publication accessible online for free under the scope of the project. We will choose the most suitable approach (either “green” OA or “gold” OA) to peer-reviewed scientific publications that might result from the project. The publisher will be chosen amongst those who respect both the authors’ interests and accept the terms of open access publication (with an embargo period). On one hand, research data will benefit from an open access in a specific part of the project website, tailored to different levels of internal and external stakeholders. On the other hand, Partners will use an open access repository that will be connected to the tools proposed by the EC (e.g., OpenAIRE), in order to grant access to the publications and bibliographic metadata in a standard format, including the information requested by the EC.

⁴ from <https://zenodo.org/communities/rotate?page=1&size=20>

4.1.3 Making data Interoperable

To be “Interoperable” means:

- (meta)data use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
(Section I1 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)
- (meta)data use vocabularies that follow “FAIR” principles.
(Section I2 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)
- (meta)data include qualified references to other (meta)data.
(Section I3 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)

As data is still being produced, the strategy used to make them interoperable will be detailed in future versions of the DMP.

4.1.4 Making data Reusable

To be “Reusable” means:

- R1. (meta)data is richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes.
(Section I1 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)
- R1.1. (meta)data is released with a clear and accessible data usage license.
(Section I1 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)
- R1.2. (meta)data is associated with detailed provenance.
(Section I1 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)
- R1.3. (meta)data meets domain-relevant community standards.
(Section I1 page 19 from https://ec.europa.eu/info/sites/default/files/turning_fair_into_reality_0.pdf)

To render data reusable, the ROTATE consortium will discuss how to add value to the data. The vision will be more precise in the DMP V2 (M46) as we do not have sufficient information at this stage of the project.

4.2 GDPR

Within the European Union, during the early stages of the internet, the 1995 Data Protection Directive was adopted. Over the last 25 years, tremendous changes in technology brought forth the need to revise data protection regulations. In 2016, the EU adopted the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR), which is now recognized as law across the EU.

GDPR has been enforced in 2018 and provides broader data privacy for individuals, as well as new obligations for any data-processing Organization (data collector, publisher, implementor), regardless of geographical location, that collects, uses, or processes European Union citizens' personal information. Personal data security is thus improved via the enforcement of the four following aspects.

- **Right to be forgotten:** Article 17 mentions the obligation of the Organization, and any business partners with whom they have shared data, to delete any personal data from their systems upon request.
- **Data protection by design and default:** Article 25 stipulates that Organizations must set internal policies and measures to protect data by design and default, and that all applications, services, and products must adhere to these policies.
- **Secure data processing:** Article 32 requires that Organizations be able to prove an implementation of measures to ensure appropriate levels of security.
- **Timely breach notifications:** Article 34 imposes hefty fines to Organizations if breaches of unencrypted data are not reported to authorities and affected individuals within 72 hours.

GDPR has been identified as one of the targets of ROTATE. In reality, the current context of the Project shows a variety of factors bringing different barriers and obstacles for it to reach higher TRL. Amongst the legal factors, GDPR plays a data protection role and its purpose limitation (requirement that personal data be collected for specified, explicit, and legitimate purposes, and not be processed further in a manner incompatible with those purposes) can hinder our progress. For this reason, ROTATE will anticipate these limitations thanks to legal studies in WP9, and include an assessment of factors influencing data governance, including applicable legal regimes such as the GDPR.

4.2.1 Personal Data Collection, Processing, and Re-use

A limited number of ROTATE partners will be involved in personal data collection and processing. They will also be involved in tracking or observation of participants arising from Datasets and in further processing of previously collected personal data (i.e., secondary use). ROTATE will be subject to the provisions of the GDPR that enshrines the following key principles (without considering exemptions):

1. Data must be processed fairly, lawfully, and only for the purpose for which it was collected and further processed.
2. Data cannot be disclosed without authorization unless there is an overriding act of law or legitimate grounds to do so.
3. Subject to certain exemptions, individuals have a right to access the information relating to them and to ask for correction of inaccurate data.
4. Information cannot be transferred beyond the EEA boundaries without consent or adoption of other adequate protection measures.
5. Organizations are usually required to register or notify the processing of personal data unless the data processing is simplistic, or a data protection officer has been appointed.
6. Organization must have adequate security measures in place.
7. The ROTATE consortium exercises a principal of minimum resort to notification exemptions afforded under national laws.

4.2.2 Personal Data Collection, Processing, and Re-use

Data management activities concern the whole project and need to be coordinated and monitored both at project and work package level. Data management is also linked to publication of project results and thus dissemination activities. Therefore, the following roles and responsibilities can be identified:

The Data Protection Officer (T9.4 task leader) is responsible for:

- Developing the data management plan and policy in cooperation with the project management in WP9 and the technical partners.
- Developing a user guide for the usage of ROTATE living DMP.
- Advise data controllers and processors within the ROTATE project on the processing of personal data, training of researchers and assignment of responsibilities.
- Assist in risk assessment of personal data processing.
- Monitoring data management activities (both collection and publication) and deadlines and sending reminders to WP data managers.
- Providing support to WP data managers.
- Coordinating the writing of the DMP deliverable documents (D9.9 - 9-10).
- Providing solutions for specific issues in accordance with project management.
- Cooperate with any national or European supervisory authority and act as contact point for the project with such authorities.

The Work Package Data Managers (AKKODIS) are responsible for:

- The implementation of the data management policy in their respective WPs.
- Monitoring data management activities and deadlines and sending reminders to partners.
- Offering customized help and further guidance for using ROTATE's living DMP.
- Asking partners for missing information or clarifications.
- Offering customized help and further guidance for publishing open data and open-source software.

- Monitoring that open results (data and software) are deposited in the default repository or a complementary OpenAIRE-compliant repository and sending reminders to partners.
- Monitoring that open results available in OpenAIRE are properly linked (OpenAIRE ROTATE) with ROTATE.
- Contacting the quality assurance and ethics committee in case of questions and ethical and privacy issues that may forbid a publication of the data.
- Ensuring that the meta-data of data used and produced at Work Package-level is made available in ROTATE's living DMP according to the ROTATE data management policy and guidelines in a timely manner.

4.2.3 Compliance with GDPR Recital 78

Personal Data within the scope of the Directive. It is necessary for the data to be related to an identified or identifiable living individual. The individual need not be directly identifiable but may be identified by a reference number or some other tag which, in a given small group or through analysis of patterns in sufficient volumes of data, might allow an individual to be singled out from a group. Based on the kinds of data sources to be included in this research, direct personal identifiers (e.g., specific names or faces) may exist in a variety of locations within the dataset. ROTATE's default anonymization process(es) will be 'one-way,' with original source data being disposed, so that re-identification of data or decoding of anonymization tokens by reference to any 'real-world' data sets will be rendered difficult to the greatest extent possible.

ROTATE will include downstream contractual obligations as a legal measure to respecting privacy in the use of the project results.

4.2.4 Data Protection Agency Notification

The data processed in ROTATE is unlikely to constitute Personal Data within the meaning of the EU Directive and relevant national legislation. ROTATE is also likely to be exempted from national notification processes because our data collection is for the purposes of scientific research and, thus additional institutional data protection measures, access restrictions, etc. will be put in place. We are, nevertheless, mindful that anonymization approaches must be applied to video/still images within data to avoid the risk that a token identifier might become associated with sufficient unique data points to uniquely identify a living individual. We also make sure to notify data protection authorities in jurisdictions where research activities will be carried out and specific relevant actions within it in order to obtain (if necessary) authorization for such activities. The exact requirements and due diligence will need to be scoped and defined within the relevant jurisdictions.

The relevant national approvals will be sought and acquired, when necessary, as the notification requirements vary from one country to another, and therefore no single timeline can be provided for completion of all notification procedures.⁵ Renewal of notifications, when necessary, will be carried out in line with requirements of different national legislations. Processes for notification

⁵ <http://ec.europa.eu/justice/policies/privacy/docs/wpdocs/others/2006-07-03-vademecum.doc>.

vary from one jurisdiction to another. The following project principals have been assigned the responsibility of acting as interlocutors with their own national data protection agency. Further information on notification procedures and the relevant agencies in Europe can be found in the *Article 29 Working Group documents* and the relevant agencies in Europe can be found in the *Article 29 Working Group document “Vademecum on Notification Requirements”*.

The exact partner and contact person who will notify the relevant Data Protection Agency will be determined during the project and after the transition from *Directive 95/46 to General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) 2016/679*.

Renewal of notifications, when necessary, will be carried out in line with the requirements of different national legislations. The renewal requirements will also be leveraged to react to change in the project and the adoption of video archives into research, development, and test tasks.

4.2.5 Compliance with Article 49 of the GDPR

While our position as scientific researchers permit us derogation from the prohibition on processing (sensitive categories of) Personal Data, we are nevertheless aware that it remains incumbent upon us, to provide specific and suitable safeguards so as to protect the fundamental rights and privacy of Data Subjects. Some of these safeguards are already detailed above. ROTATE further ensures that any Personal Data collected will also be treated in accordance with Article 49. In particular, collected Personal Data will be processed fairly and lawfully and will be used only for research purposes as specified in our original proposal. The data will be adequate, relevant, and not excessive in relation to the purposes for which they are collected. We will endeavor not to collect and to expunge all data that is not directly project-related.

4.2.6 Safe Harbor and Privacy Shield Considerations

In light of the Court of Justice of the European Union October 6th, 2015, decision on the EU-US Safe Harbor agreement, the ROTATE project will store all data derived from personal data (after anonymization or dissociation) in EU member states and comply with the Article 29 Working Groups communiques on transfer of data outside of the union and forthcoming member state decisions on Safe Harbor.

4.2.7 Activities Dedicated to Ethical Considerations

The guiding principles at the heart of the ROTATE approach are the highest ethical standards, the protection of privacy and the validity of data and its accurate representation. In adhering to these principles and remaining cognizant of concerns that arise in the Work Plan, ROTATE will take the following steps, in addition to those detailed above, toward addressing these:

- Compliance with the policy recommendations made in the Social Impact Expert Working Group EC DG ENTR Report (2012).
- The availability of partners with Ethics, Privacy and Legal expertise to all ROTATE project staff members at the outset of the project and throughout.

- Assurance that Privacy by Design, Ethics, Legal and Societal Impact requirements are included as research and development mandates integrated into the ROTATE project plan in compliance with GDPR Article 25.
- Test and evaluation of research results will be carried out in WP8 under the principal of informed consent.

4.2.8 Minimum Resort to Exceptions and Derogations

The GDPR allows for exceptions and derogations for personal data used for research. For example, general exemptions for processing of certain categories of sensitive personal data (e.g., Article 6 and Recital 50). Exceptions for a right to opposition for processing or storage of data (Article 89), and for processing of data without consent (Article 6.1.f, Recitals 47 and 157) may be applicable. ROTATE commits to a minimum resort to exceptions and derogations in the processing of personal data within the project for the purposes of research.

4.2.9 Activities Dedicated to Protection and Securing of Personal Data

As project coordinator, ANEFA shall ensure the consortium guarantees adequate treatment of personal data generated during the project. This will be done via a set of development directives and methodologies. To ensure that security systems development principles are integrated from the inception of the project best practices will be issued to RTD staff in the ROTATE project to ensure the project applies adequate database encryption and secure systems techniques.

Furthermore, the directives and mandates will also integrate the technical requirements of European, national, and regional data protection legislation. Partners will be required to have adequate security measures in place - both technical (firewalls, access controls, access audits, etc.) and operational (training, incidence reporting, etc.) As both part of the project tasks, and notification procedures, the following range of issues will be considered in establishing such directives and mandates:

- Categories of sensitive data.
- Security measures for sensitive data.
- Policies for fair acquisition and processing of data.
- Data retention policies.
- Legal Basis for the information processing.
- Policies for processing compatible with purpose.
- Policies for Data Controller and Data Processors.
- Description of the technical characteristics of the data processed.
- Technical features and topology of the information systems where data is stored and processed.

Further consideration shall be given to the following relevant regulation, decisions, and guidelines.

The following EU regulations are recognized to be relevant for the project:

- The Charter of Fundamental Rights of the EU (especially articles 3, 7, 8 and 25).
- Directive 2001/20/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 4 April 2001 on the approximation of the laws, regulations and administrative provisions of the Member States relating to the implementation of good clinical practice in the conduct of clinical trials on medicinal products for human use.

- Directive 95/46/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 24 October 1995 on the protection of individuals with regard to the processing of personal data and on the free movement of such data.
- Convention for the Protection of Individuals with Regard to Automatic Processing of Personal Data (Convention Nr. 108).
- WMA Declaration of Helsinki (especially articles 13, 20, 21, 22, 23 and 24, 25).

4.2.10 Shared Information and Personal Data

The Parties agree that any Background, Results, Confidential Information and/or any and all data and/or information that is provided, disclosed, or otherwise made available between the Parties during the implementation of the Action and/or for any Exploitation activities (“Shared Information”), shall not include personal data as defined by Article 2, Section (a) of the Data Protection Directive (95/46/EEC) (hereinafter referred to as “Personal Data”) or under Article 4.1 of the GDPR. Accordingly, each Party agrees that it will take all necessary steps to ensure that all Personal Data is removed from the Shared Information, made illegible, or otherwise made inaccessible (i.e., de-identify) to the other Parties prior to providing the Shared Information to such other Parties.

5 Allocation of resources

In the project, Kamel NEMER and Sophie TURLUR-CHABANON (AKKODIS) plays the role of Data Manager and liaises with the Technical Management Team (TMT) about the data management issues. The Data Manager leads data management plan tasks and participates in the project coordination in terms of the evaluation data collection, storage, and handling, as well as their publication as part of the ORDP.

All research data collected as part of this project is owned by the data producer or Partners involved in trial sites. The Partners in ROTATE will take the responsibility for the collection, management, and sharing of the research data. Quality assessment will be the responsibility of data manager of each trial site.

The costs to make the data “FAIR” in ROTATE shall be handled by each partner who will have to generate its data according to the requirements expressed in the Data Management Plan. Specifically, different tasks of WP9 will contribute to fulfil the requirements of FAIR principles.

6 Access and Curation

This section explains, in the first part, the strategy chosen about the access of the data (storage, access policies, licensing). The next part covers the data protection and qualification.

6.1 Data Access

6.1.1 Open Access and ORDP

Within Horizon EU/2020 (HEU/H2020), the objective is to have an open access to scientific information. The notion of open access here refers to “the practice of providing online access to scientific information that is free of charge to the end-user and reusable”⁶, where “scientific information” includes both the peer-reviewed scientific research articles/publications and the research data underlying publications, curated data, and/or raw data. To ensure open access to all peer-reviewed scientific research publications relating to project results, which is an obligation, two routes are possible.

- Self-archiving / 'green' open access - the author, or a representative, archives (deposits) machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer-reviewed manuscript in an online repository before, upon or after its publication. Some repository software delays access only after an embargo period has elapsed. If this is the case, the European Commission demands that the open access is ensured within a maximum of six months.
- Open access publishing / 'gold' open access - an article is immediately published at a publisher or on a journal website. In this model, open access must be granted at the latest on the date of publication. A copy of the publication should also be deposited in a repository.

Whichever the route chosen, HEU beneficiaries must at least ensure that any scientific peer-reviewed publications can be read online, downloaded, and printed. They must also strive to provide the right to copy, distribute, search, link, crawl, and mine to the public, in order to make publications more useful. As mentioned previously (cf. 3.1.2 supra), peer-reviewed scientific publications resulting from the project will become accessible openly, thanks to an open access repository used by partners, connected to the tools proposed by the EC (e.g., openAIRE), which grants access to the publications and bibliographic metadata in a standard format, including the information requested by the EC.

With regard to the openness of research data, the Open Research Data Pilot (ORDP) run by the European Commission “aims to improve and maximize access to and re-use of research data generated by HEU projects and takes into account the need to balance openness and protection of scientific information, commercialization, and Intellectual Property Rights (IPR), privacy concerns, security as well as data management and preservation questions.” This ORDP applies primarily to the digital form data needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications, including statistics, results of experiments, measurements, observations resulting from fieldwork, survey results, interview recordings and images. Users can normally access, mine, exploit, reproduce and disseminate openly accessible research data free of charge.

Despite the benefits of open access, some research data cannot be made open. For this reason, the principle of “as open as possible, as closed as necessary” applies. It is therefore “possible to

⁶ https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-dissemination_en.htm

opt out of research data sharing at any stage - before or after the signature of the grant agreement - but reasons have to be given e.g., for intellectual property rights (IPR) concerns, privacy/data protection concerns, national security concern, if it would run against the main objective of the project or for other legitimate reasons.”, precisely the same potential reasons which may play a role in the balance.

In order to specify the type of data subject to open access, a Data Management Plan (DMP) is required, which is the subject of this present deliverable. The management of scientific information within HEU under the open access guidelines is illustrated as follows.

Figure 4 Open access to research data⁷

As mentioned in the Grant Agreement, ROTATE is committed to ORDP.

As already explained previously, the two pillars to ORDP consist of “the development of a Data Management Plan (DMP) and the open access to research data, if possible⁸. The first point is being addressed by the establishment of a DMP as a deliverable of ROTATE and by its maintenance. The second point will be fulfilled by the open access to research data including public deliverables, non-protected results or results coming after a patent registration, which will be rendered throughout the whole project’s duration in a specific part of the project website, tailored to different levels of internal and external stakeholders but also published on a general-purpose open repository like Zenodo. The partners will agree altogether on the data that are shareable and the ones that are confidential and that should remain in the consortium only.

6.1.2 Data licensing

⁷ from: (https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/cross-cutting-issues/open-access-data-management/open-access_en.htm: section 2 Research data).

⁸ <https://www.openaire.eu/what-is-the-open-research-data-pilot>

For example, Creative Commons Corporation (CC) has introduced a well-known system of licenses⁹. CC licenses are free of charge and easy to use since any license consists of a legally binding arrangement, a summary, a symbol which may be downloaded as a graphics file and inserted in a document, and a machine-readable symbol. Their public copyright licenses incorporate a unique and innovative “three-layer” design: Legal Code, Commons Deed and CC REL. This type of license may be used for the protection of all types of content. It also makes the concept understandable by the creators of works, uses, and the Web itself.

Besides, Open-Source Initiative (OSI) approves some licenses which comply with the Open-Source Definition, and which have gone through the OSI license review process. Such approved licenses¹⁰ allow software to be freely used, modified, and shared. They include Apache, GNU, MIT, Mozilla, just to mention the most popular ones. The Consortium will choose the most appropriate licenses for use depending on the type of data concerned.

6.1.3 Storage

In the European framework, European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) is an initiative providing a world-class data infrastructure for storing and managing data. It arises from the EC’s aim to promote the access and reuse of research data that comes out of publicly funded research. Under Horizon EU, EOSC becomes the best instrument to provide a framework for collaboration and the pooling of resources at European, national, regional, and institutional levels¹¹. In particular, EOSC aims at solving the problem of fragmented access and non-interoperable research data centres across Europe. In terms of data storage, EOSC provides several reliable, secure, and scalable cloud storage solutions for scientific data, apps and workloads. Amongst them, some are of open access or even fully open access. For example, BlueBRIDGE suggests an Online environment to support secure and controlled data sharing and storage, INRIA Software Heritage archive is a great library of source code on engineering and technology sciences, and Institute of Informatics of Slovak Academy of Sciences offers EGI FedCloud client.

EOSC also provides other services such as Open Science (OS) publishing infrastructure which is connected to the EOSC. OpenAIRE is one such an example which contributes actively to EOSC.¹⁴ On one hand, OpenAIRE provides a cost-free data repository (Zenodo), allowing data deposit and discovery, rendering data Accessible. On the other hand, through harvesting repositories and mining techniques, OpenAIRE infers links between publications, research funding, and research data, which enables data Reuse.

As mentioned in the previous section concerning Open access, ROTATE partners will use such an open access repository as OpenAIRE, in order to grant access to the publications and

⁹ <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/>

¹⁰ <https://opensource.org/licenses>

¹¹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/about/eosc>

bibliographic metadata in a standard format. Specifically, Zenodo is a repository where every upload is assigned a Digital Object Identifier (DOI), making them citable, trackable, and thus Findable. It also provides flexible Access conditions. Zenodo also ensures interoperability by allowing GitHub integration to preserve metadata. Finally, its versioning gives the possibility to update datasets easily and store all changes in metadata over record's lifetime, which enable Reuse. To summarize, these advantages are totally compliant with the FAIR principles.

6.1.4 Authentication and authorization

During their storage, data should be protected against any type of modification by the implementation of some security principles. The security principles are listed below:

- **Authentication:** All the users wanting to get access to the ROTATE data servers should be authenticated. Also, proper means are used to authenticate the servers. An authentication system could be used to handle the authentication of the users during the project.
- **Authorization:** the access to ROTATE data servers is only available to the authenticated and authorized users. These categories and the rights of those users are defined and enforced. The appropriate access control policies and mechanisms (including physical access control) shall be identified project wide and for each trial site. Those actions are necessary to ensure the security of the data.
- **Accounting:** In ROTATE, any access and modification to a resource by any user is securely logged in order to prevent users from denying that data files were accessed, altered, or deleted. Other accounting mechanisms shall be implemented.
- **Confidentiality:** the data stored in ROTATE servers should be encrypted during transmission and storage.
- **Communication Security:** Access to ROTATE servers should be done through encrypted communication channels such as HTTPS and IPsec.
- **Data Integrity:** The data collected during ROTATE should be protected from malicious and accidental modifications by any users during their transmission or their storage. Cryptographic mechanisms such as hash functions and digital signatures shall be used.
- **Availability:** This security principle assures that the ROTATE servers should be available for ROTATE users during the defined interval of service. Also, regular backups of the data should be made. Therefore, mechanisms to cope with the charge and DoS attacks should be implemented.

6.2 Data qualification and curation

6.2.1 Data protection

Securing stored digital data involves preventing unauthorized people from accessing it, as well as preventing accidental or intentional destruction, infection, or corruption of information. While data encryption is a popular mechanism, it is just one of many techniques and technologies that can be used to implement a tiered data-security strategy. Steps to secure data involve understanding applicable threats, aligning appropriate layers of defense, and continual monitoring of activity logs taking action as needed. This means that a multi-tier approach needs to be adopted from all the partners.

The proper method of storage and the appropriate community along with levels of access for privileged users are important considerations for comprehensive protection. Improperly stored

information along with overly permissive accounts are a centralized theme in many high-profile breaches. Partners within ROTATE will follow a specific set of guidelines to comply with the project's main requirement for storage of digital data.

- Data availability must be guaranteed.
- Confidential data must be stored using access protection.
- Strictly confidential information must only be stored in an encrypted mode.
- Confidential data must not be stored in online services that are not approved by the ROTATE Consortium.
- Any exception from this measure must explicitly be approved.
- Modifications to data with high integrity requirements must be documented and approved by the partners.

6.2.2 Data qualification

The aim of the data qualification is to clarify and thoroughly document the semantics of the data, which facilitates subsequent data analysis. If there is an original data documentation, it typically focuses on what is of interest to the management or the auditors. Yet, data qualification allows to the exploration of the semantics of the data in detail, which then be updated or specified with this documentation. Indeed, data qualification allows to understand and reveal the gap between the perceived semantics of current data Analyzers and the true and underlying semantic of the data.

Data is dynamic and requires constant maintenance. Data qualification should thus be constantly carried out, so as to keep the data up-to-date, valid, accurate and reliable. In order to operate data qualification, additional computation is needed to implement rules for different processes of data verification, validation, approvals, and rejection, which then generates metadata. Although qualifying data necessitates additional resources and efforts, better qualified data delivers higher quality and consistency, which helps with decision making and clarifies the direction of further research.

7 Conclusions

This Data Management Plan V1 gives a first overview of the data processed in ROTATE and describes the data categories of the project, providing information on their management and on the implementation of the FAIR principles in the project. ROTATE will be committed to following the principles of the Horizon EU Open Research Data Pilot, and therefore the guidelines associated with open access have been described, with the aim to ensure that the project's outputs will be openly available to the research community.

Towards the Data Management Plan V2:

It is important to note that the Data Management Plan is a living document and will be constantly updated until the end of the ROTATE project. The present document is the first version of the Data Management Plan, and in the next version (D9.10, 2nd issue), more details will be provided, especially regarding the description of shared datasets, and corresponding standards and methodologies. A great consideration will be given to datasets to be shared in the course of the VEL labs (WP5) and for which we do not yet have sufficient information at this stage of the project. These different categories of data require different treatments and the definition by the project of an appropriate methodology (for example anonymization of personal traveler data). In the same way, the data from our reference group of stakeholders will be detailed, and their specificities duly described.

ROTATE Consortium

The consortium of ROTATE consists of 21 partners with multidisciplinary and complementary competencies. This includes leading universities, networks, and industry sector specialists.

 <https://www.linkedin.com/company/rotate8/>

 <https://twitter.com/RotateProject>

 https://www.instagram.com/rotate_project/

 <https://www.facebook.com/Rotate-105023652344772>

 https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCord7CyGj_VUsV2AaQMgfBQ

 <https://vimeo.com/user184305085>

For further information please visit <https://rotateproject.eu/>

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